

Optimal stopping of Gauss-Markov bridges with random pinning point

Abel Azze^{1,2}

Abstract

We study an Optimal Stopping Problem (OSP) for Gauss–Markov processes conditioned to hit a prescribed terminal distribution. Using a time-space transformation, we show that this OSP is equivalent to that of a Brownian bridge with a random pinning point. This allows us to characterize the optimal stopping time as the first hitting time into the stopping region, and establish continuity and higher smoothness of the value function, as well as to obtain the free-boundary formulation of the problem. We also derive comparison results showing that value functions are ordered by the likelihood-ratio order of terminal densities. When terminal densities are Gaussian or degenerate at a point, the transformed drift simplifies, and optimal stopping boundaries are uniquely characterized by Volterra-type integral equations. Finally, we analyze a two-point terminal distribution, revealing that, despite its apparent simplicity, the stopping region exhibits an unexpectedly complex structure.

Keywords: Optimal stopping; diffusion process; Time-inhomogeneity, Brownian bridge, Gauss-Markov processes.

1 Random Gauss-Markov bridges

1.1 Gauss-Markov processes

For a terminal time $T > 0$ and an initial condition $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, consider a standard Brownian Motion (BM) $B = (B_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}_+}$ defined in the probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. Let $X = (X_t)_{t \in [0, T]}$ be the unique strong solution of the Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE)

$$\begin{cases} dX_t = (\alpha(t) + \beta(t)X_t) dt + \zeta(t)dB_t, \\ X_0 = x_0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\beta : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and $\zeta : [0, T] \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ are continuous functions. Such a process X , besides being Markovian, is also Gaussian, with normal transition probability density (see, e.g., Buonocore et al. (2013)) defined by the mean and variance functions

$$m_{t,x}(u) := \mathbb{E}[X_{t'} | X_t = x] = \varphi(t, t') \left(x + \int_t^{t'} \frac{\alpha(u)}{\varphi(t, u)} du \right), \quad (2)$$

$$v_t^2(t') := \text{Var}[X_{t'} | X_t = x] = \varphi^2(t, t') \int_t^{t'} \frac{\zeta^2(u)}{\varphi^2(t, u)} du, \quad (3)$$

with $0 \leq t < t' \leq T$, and for

$$\varphi(t, t') := \exp \left\{ \int_t^{t'} \beta(u) du \right\}. \quad (4)$$

It is also known (see, e.g., Borisov (1983)) that the (auto)covariance of X admits the “factorization”

$$\text{Cov}[X_t, X_{t'}] = r_1(\min(t, t'))r_2(\max(t, t')),$$

¹Department of Quantitative Methods, CUNEF Universidad (Spain).

²Corresponding author. e-mail: abel.guada@cunef.edu.

for the unique-up-to-multiplicative-constants functions

$$r_1(t) = \varphi(0, t) \int_0^t \frac{\zeta^2(u)}{\varphi^2(0, u)} du, \quad r_2(t) = \varphi(0, t).$$

Moreover (see, e.g., Mehr and McFadden (1965)), X admits the BM representation

$$X_t = m_{0, x_0}(t) + r_2(t)B_{h(t)} = m(t) + \varphi(t) (B_{h(t)} + x_0), \quad (5)$$

for $h(t) := r_1(t)/r_2(t)$, $m(t) := m_{0,0}(t)$, and $\varphi(t) := \varphi(0, t)$.

1.2 The standard BM representation

Note that $h(t) = r_1(t)/r_2(t)$ is a strictly increasing function ranging from $h(0) = 0$ to $\mathbb{T} := h(T)$. Hence, by defining the change of time and auxiliary functions

$$s = s(t) = h(t)/\mathbb{T}, \quad a_0(s) := m(h^{-1}(s)), \quad a_1(s) := \varphi(h^{-1}(s))\sqrt{\mathbb{T}}, \quad (6)$$

we obtain from (5) and the scale property of a BM, that

$$X_t = G(s, Y_s), \quad s \in [0, 1], \quad (7)$$

where $(Y_s)_{s \in [0,1]}$ is a BM starting at $Y_0 = x_0$, and G takes the form

$$G(s, y) := a_0(s) + a_1(s)y. \quad (8)$$

From the definition of a_0 and a_1 in (6) and (2)-(4), and the continuity of α , β and ζ in $[0, T]$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 \text{ and } a_1 \text{ are continuously differentiable in } [0, 1], \\ a_1(s) > 0 \text{ for all } s \in [0, 1], \end{aligned}$$

and the following positive constants are well defined:

$$A_0 := \sup_{s \in \mathbb{R}_+} |a_0(s)|, \quad A'_0 := \sup_{s \in \mathbb{R}_+} |a'_0(s)|, \quad A_1 := \sup_{s \in \mathbb{R}_+} a_1(s), \quad A'_1 := \sup_{s \in \mathbb{R}_+} |a'_1(s)|. \quad (9)$$

1.3 Conditioning on a terminal density

Given a density function ν in \mathbb{R} , define the rescaled density

$$\nu(z; x_0, T) := \nu((z - m(T))/\varphi(T) - x_0),$$

and introduce the probability \mathbb{P}^ν such that $\mathbb{P}^\nu(\cdot) = \mathbb{P}(\cdot \mid X_T \sim \nu(\cdot; x_0, T))$. That is, X_T is distributed according to $\nu(\cdot; x_0, T)$ under \mathbb{P}^ν . From (6) to (8), this is equivalent to make Y_1 adopt the original density ν , meaning that $\mathbb{P}(\cdot \mid X_T \sim \nu_{x_0, T}) = \mathbb{P}(\cdot \mid Y_1 \sim \nu)$. By means of the Girsanov theorem (see Proposition 7), under \mathbb{P}^ν , $(Y_s)_{s \in [0,1]}$ solves the SDE

$$\begin{cases} dY_s = \mu^\nu(s, Y_s)ds + dB_s^\nu, \\ Y_0 = x_0, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

for the \mathbb{P}^ν -standard BM $B^\nu = (B_s^\nu)_{s \in [0,1]}$, and for the drift function

$$\mu^\nu(s, y) = \partial_y \ln(\psi^\nu(s, y)), \quad (11)$$

where ψ^ν is the Radon-Nikodym density $\mathbb{P}^\nu / \mathbb{P}$, defined as

$$\psi^\nu(s, y \mid 0, x_0) = \psi^\nu(s, y) := \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\phi(z; y, 1-s)}{\phi(z; x_0, 1)} \nu(z) dz, \quad (12)$$

where $\phi(z; \theta, \gamma^2)$ represents the normal density with mean θ and variance γ^2 . Here and thereafter, we use ∂_s and ∂_y to refer to the partial derivative to respect to the time and space components, and ∂_{yy} to indicate the second space partial derivative.

1.4 Random Brownian bridges

From the random nature of the pinning point, we call the process defined at (10) a random Brownian Bridge (rBB). A straightforward differentiation yields

$$\mu^\nu(s, y) = \partial_y \ln(\psi^\nu(s, y)) = \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{z-y}{1-t} \frac{\phi(z; y, 1-s)}{\phi(z; x_0, 1)} \nu(z) dz}{\int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\phi(z; y, 1-s)}{\phi(z; x_0, 1)} \nu(z) dz} = \frac{\mathbb{E}^\nu [Z_{s,y}] - y}{1-s}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbb{E}^ν is the expectation with respect to \mathbb{P}^ν , and $Z_{s,y}$ is the random pinning point, whose density, updated by observing the process up to $Y_s = y$, is given by

$$\nu_{s,y}(z) = \partial_z \mathbb{P}^\nu (B_1 \leq z | Y_s = y) = \frac{\phi(z; y, 1-s)}{\phi(z; x_0, 1)} \nu(z) / \psi^\nu(s, y). \quad (14)$$

In the sequel, we rely on the following assumption.

Assumption 1 (Regularity of the terminal density).

For all $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, there exist a constant $L_\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\text{Var} [Z_{s,y}] \leq L_\varepsilon$ for all $(s, y) \in (0, 1 - \varepsilon) \times \mathbb{R}$.

The next proposition obtains a Lipschitz-type bound for the distance of the pinning points provided different initial conditions. This property will prove itself useful to obtain bound of the partial derivatives of the value function associated to rBBs.

Proposition 1 (L_1 -Lipschitz continuity of the pinning point with respect to time).

For $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, let $\pi^* = \pi_{s,y_1,y_2}^*$ be the optimal coupling that gives the Wasserstein-1 distance between ν_{s,y_1} and ν_{s,y_2} . That is,

$$\mathbb{E}^{\pi^*} [|Z_{s,y_1} - Z_{s,y_2}|] = \mathcal{W}(\nu_{s,y_1}, \nu_{s,y_2}) := \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\nu_{s,y_1}, \nu_{s,y_2})} \mathbb{E}^\pi [|Z_{s,y_1} - Z_{s,y_2}|], \quad (15)$$

where $\Pi(f, g)$ is the set of all couplings whose marginal densities are f and g . Then, under Assumption 1, for all $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists a constant $L_\varepsilon > 0$ such that,

$$\mathbb{E}^{\pi^*} [|Z_{s,y_1} - Z_{s,y_2}|] \leq L_\varepsilon |y_1 - y_2|, \quad (16)$$

for all $s \in (0, 1 - \varepsilon)$.

Proof. The following is a well-known bound (see Proposition 7.10 from Villani (2003)) of the Wasserstein-1 distance:

$$\mathcal{W}(\nu_{s,y_1}, \nu_{s,y_2}) \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}} |z| |\nu_{s,y_1}(z) - \nu_{s,y_2}(z)| dz. \quad (17)$$

Straightforward differentiation of (14) yields that $\partial_y \nu_{s,y}(z) = \nu_{s,y}(z) \frac{z - \mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]}{1-s}$, from where it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}} |z| |\partial_y \nu_{s,y}(z)| dz &\leq \frac{1}{1-s} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \nu_{s,y}(z) |z| |z - \mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]| dz \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1-s} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} \nu_{s,y}(z) (z - \mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}])^2 dz + |\mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]| \int_{\mathbb{R}} \nu_{s,y}(z) |z - \mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]| dz \right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1-s} \left(\text{Var} [Z_{s,y}] + |\mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]| \sqrt{\text{Var} [Z_{s,y}]} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where, in the second inequality, we used the triangular inequality $|z| \leq |z - \mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]| + |\mathbb{E}[Z_{s,y}]|$. Hence, the proof of part 1 is an immediate consequence of Assumption 1, inequality (17), and the fact that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} |z| |\nu_{s,y_1}(z) - \nu_{s,y_2}(z)| dz \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}} |z| \int_{y_1}^{y_2} |\partial_y \nu_{s,y}(z)| dy dz \leq \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} |z| |\partial_y \nu_{s,y}(z)| dz dy.$$

□

2 The equivalent optimal stopping problems

Consider now the Optimal Stopping Problem (OSP)

$$V(t, x) = \sup_{\tau \leq T-t} \mathbb{E}_{t,x}^\nu [X_{t+\tau}], \quad (18)$$

where the supremum is taken among all stopping times of $(X_{t+u})_{u \in [0, T-t]}$, and $\mathbb{E}_{t,x}^\nu$ is the mean operator with respect to the probability measure $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}^\nu$, defined such that $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}^\nu(\cdot) = \mathbb{P}^\nu(\cdot | X_t = x)$. For later use, we also introduce the probability measure $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}$ such that $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}[\cdot] = \mathbb{P}(\cdot | X_t = x)$.

2.1 The equivalent optimal stopping problem of a random Brownian bridge

We also define the transformed OSP

$$W(s, y) = \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s} \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [G(s + \sigma, Y_{s+\sigma})], \quad (19)$$

for the gain function G defined at (8), and where the supremum is taken among stopping times of the process $(Y_{s+u})_{u \in [0, 1-s]}$, which is a $\mathbb{P}_{s,y}$ -BM starting at $Y_s = y$. We claim that solving (18) is equivalent to solve (19), in the sense specified by the following proposition.

Proposition 2 (Equivalence of the OSPs).

Let V and W be the value functions in (18) and (19). For $(t, x) \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}$, take $s = h(t)$ and $y = (x - m(t)) / \gamma(t)$. Then,

$$V(t, x) = W(s, y). \quad (20)$$

Moreover, $\tau^* = \tau^*(t, x)$ is an OST for V if and only if $\sigma^* = \sigma^*(s, y)$, defined such that $s + \sigma^* = h(t + \tau^*)$, is an OST for W .

Proof. From (5), we obtain the following representation for X_{t+u} under $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}$:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{t+u} &= m(t+u) + \varphi(t+u) (B_{h(t+u)} + x_0) \\ &= m(t+u) + \varphi(t+u) (B_{h(t+u)} - B_{h(t)} + y), \end{aligned}$$

where we used, also based on (5), that $B_{h(t)} = y - x_0$ under $\mathbb{P}_{t,x}$. Taking $r = h(t+u) - h(t)$ and $Y_{s+r} := B_{s+r} - B_s + y$, we obtain that $X_{t+u} = G(s+r, Y_{s+r})$.

For every stopping time τ of $(X_{t+u})_{u \in [0, T-t]}$, define the stopping time σ of $(Y_{s+r})_{r \in [0, 1-s]}$ such that $s + \sigma = h(t + \tau)$. Hence, (20) is a consequence of

$$V(t, x) = \sup_{\tau \leq T-t} \mathbb{E}_{t,x}^\nu [X_{t+\tau}] = \sup_{\sigma \geq 0} \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [G(s + \sigma, Y_{s+\sigma})] = W(s, y).$$

Furthermore, suppose that $\tau^* = \tau^*(t, x)$ is an OST for (18) and that there exists a stopping time $\sigma' = \sigma'(s, y)$ that performs better than $\sigma^* = \sigma^*(s, y)$ in (19). Consider $\tau' = \tau'(t, x)$ such that $t + \tau' = h^{-1}(s + \sigma')$. Then,

$$\mathbb{E}_{t,x}^\nu [X_{t+\tau'}] = \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [G(s + \sigma', Y_{s+\sigma'})] > \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [G(s + \sigma^*, Y_{s+\sigma^*})] = \mathbb{E}_{t,x}^\nu [X_{t+\tau^*}],$$

which conflicts with the optimality of τ^* . Analogous arguments ensures that the optimality of σ^* in (19) implies that of τ^* in (18). \square

3 Analysis of the transformed optimal stopping problem

Keeping in mind that the original OSP of a rGMB (18) can be seen through the lens of an OSP of the simpler rBB (19), we now obtain results on the later that immediately translate to the former.

Denote by $\sigma^* = \sigma^*(s, y)$ to the first time the process $((s + u, Y_{s+u}))_{u \in [0, 1-s]}$, starting at (s, y) , hits the (stopping) closed set $\mathcal{D} := \{(s, y) : W(s, y) = G(s, y)\}$. That is,

$$\sigma^* = \sigma^*(s, y) := \inf \{u \geq 0 : (s + u, Y_u^{s,y}) \in \mathcal{D}\}.$$

where we define $(Y_u^{s,y})_{s \in [0, 1-s]}$ such that

$$\text{Law} \left((Y_u^{s,y})_{s \in [0, 1-s]}, \mathbb{P} \right) = \text{Law} \left((Y_{s+u})_{s \in [0, 1-s]}, \mathbb{P}_{s,y} \right).$$

Proposition 3 (Optimal stopping time characterization).

The first hitting time σ^ is optimal in (19). That is,*

$$W(s, y) = \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [G(s + \sigma^*, Y_{s+\sigma^*})]. \quad (21)$$

Proof. On the set $\{Z_{s,y} = z\}$, the process Y_{s+u} becomes a BB from $Y_s = y$ to $Y_1 = Z_{s,y} = z$. Then, using (30) from Lemma (1),

$$\mathbb{E}_{s,y} \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s} |Y_{s+u}| \right] = \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu \left[\mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s} |Y_{s+u}| \mid Y_1 \right] \right] \leq \sqrt{2\pi} \ln(2) + |y| + \mathbb{E} [|Z_{s,y}|] < \infty, \quad (22)$$

where we recall that the random pinning point $Z_{s,y}$ has finite second moment due to Assumption 1. From (8) along with the continuity of $a_0(s)$ and $a_1(s)$ on $[0, 1]$, we get that

$$\mathbb{E}_{s,y} \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s} |G(s + u, Y_{s+u})| \right] < \infty, \quad (23)$$

for all $(s, y) \in [0, 1) \times \mathbb{R}$. This regularity along with the continuity of the gain function G (see, e.g., Corollary 2.9 and Remark 2.10 from Peskir and Shiryaev (2006)) concludes the proof. \square

The next proposition obtains the continuity of the value function. Classical methods to obtain such regularity (see, e.g., Krylov (1980, Chapter 3) and Peskir and Shiryaev (2006)) do not work under a explosive drift. However, truncating the time component away from the horizon embeds the problem back into classical frameworks.

Proposition 4 (Continuity of the value function).

The value function W is continuous in $[0, 1) \times \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, For all compact of the form $\mathcal{K} = [0, 1-\varepsilon) \times \mathcal{R} \subset (0, 1) \times \mathbb{R}$, there exists a constant $L_{\mathcal{K}} > 0$ such that

$$W(s_1, y_1) - W(s_2, y_2) \leq L_{\mathcal{K}} (|s_1 - s_2|^{1/2} + |y_1 - y_2|),$$

that is, W is 1/2-Hölder continuous in the time component and Lipschitz continuous in the space component in compacts of $(0, 1) \times \mathbb{R}$.

Proof. Take $0 < s_1 \leq s_2 < 1$ and $y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$. Since $|\sup_\sigma a_\sigma - \sup_\sigma b_\sigma| \leq \sup_\sigma |a_\sigma - b_\sigma|$, and due to Jensen's inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} & |W(s_1, y_1) - W(s_2, y_2)| \\ &= \left| \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s_1} \mathbb{E}_{s_1, y_1}^\nu [G(s_1 + \sigma, Y_{s_1+\sigma})] - \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s_2} \mathbb{E}_{s_2, y_2}^\nu [G(s_2 + \sigma, Y_{s_2+\sigma})] \right| \\ &= \left| \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s_1} \mathbb{E}_{s_1, y_1}^\nu [G(s_1 + \sigma, Y_{s_1+\sigma})] - \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s_1} \mathbb{E}_{s_2, y_2}^\nu [G(s_2 + \sigma \wedge (1-s_2), Y_{s_2+\sigma \wedge (1-s_2)})] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} \left| G(s_1 + u, Y_u^{s_1, y_1}) - G(s_2 + u \wedge (1-s_2), Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_2}) \right| \right] \\
&\leq \left(A'_0 + A'_1 \mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1}| \right] \right) (s_2 - s_1) + A_1 \mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} \left| Y_u^{s_1, y_1} - Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_1} \right| \right], \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

where we recall the shape of G in (8) and the bounding constants in (9) to obtain the last inequality.

We can now use (32) from Lemma 1 and recall the boundedness of $\mathbb{E}^\nu [\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1}|]$ proven in (22), to get the bound

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} \left| Y_u^{s_1, y_1} - Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_1} \right| \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\mathbb{E}^\nu \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s_1} \left| Y_u^{s_1, y_1} - Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_1} \right| \mid Z_{s_1, y_1}, Z_{s_2, y_2} \right] \right] \\
&\leq K_{s_1, s_2, y_1, y_2} (s_2 - s_1) + 2\sqrt{s_2 - s_1} + |y_1 - y_2| + 3 \mathbb{E} [|Z_{s_1, y_1} - Z_{s_2, y_2}|], \quad (25)
\end{aligned}$$

for a constant $K > 0$, whenever $(s_1, y_1), (s_2, y_2) \in \mathcal{R}$.

Therefore, since $\mathbb{E} [|Z_{s_1, y_1} - Z_{s_2, y_2}|] \rightarrow 0$ as $|s_1 - s_2| \rightarrow 0$ and $|y_1 - y_2| \rightarrow 0$ (which can be direct checked from (14)), plugging (25) back into (24), we readily obtain the continuity of W in $(0, 1) \times \mathbb{R}$. \square

Denote by \mathbb{L}_Y the infinitesimal generator of the time-space process $((s, Y_s))_{s \in [0, 1]}$. That is, for a suitable function f ,

$$(\mathbb{L}_Y f)(s, y) = \partial_s f(s, y) + \mu^\nu(s, y) \partial_y f(s, y) + \frac{1}{2} \partial_{yy} f(s, y). \quad (26)$$

Introduce the (continuation) open set $\mathcal{C} := \mathcal{D}^c = \{(s, y) : W(s, y) > G(s, y)\}$.

The so-far proven regularity of the value function, along with the smoothness of the drift and diffusion coefficients in (10), suffice to proof that the solution of the OSP (19) also solves a two-phase Free-Boundary Problem (FBP) with \mathbb{L}_Y as the (parabolic) differential operator and \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} as the two phases. The boundary between these two faces, $\partial \mathcal{D}$, is called the Optimal Stopping Boundary (OSB). Further details about this connection between OSPs and FBPs can be found in Peskir and Shiryaev (2006, Chapter III, Section 7).

Proposition 5 (The free-boundary problem). *The value function satisfies $W \in C^{1,2}(\mathcal{C})$ and, together with the OSB $\partial \mathcal{D}$, solves the free-boundary problem*

$$\mathbb{L}_Y W = 0 \quad \text{on } \mathcal{C} \quad (27a)$$

$$W = G \quad \text{on } \partial \mathcal{D} \quad (\text{instantaneous stop}) \quad (27b)$$

Proof. Since W is continuous on \mathcal{C} (see Proposition 4) and the coefficients of the parabolic operator \mathbb{L}_Y satisfy sufficient smoothness conditions (local α -Hölder continuity suffice) classical results in parabolic partial differential equations (Friedman, 1964, Section 3, Theorem 9) guarantee that, for any open rectangle $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathcal{C}$, the boundary value problem

$$\begin{cases} \mathbb{L}_Y f = 0, & \text{in } \mathcal{R}, \\ f = W, & \text{on } \partial \mathcal{R}, \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

admits a unique solution $f \in C^{1,2}(\mathcal{R})$.

Applying Itô's formula to $f(s+u, Y_{s+u})$ and evaluating at $u = \sigma_{\mathcal{R}} = \inf\{u \geq 0 : (s+u, Y_{s+u}) \notin \mathcal{R}\}$, and then taking expectations under $\mathbb{P}_{s,y}^\nu$ -expectation for $(s, y) \in \mathcal{R}$ and using the strong Markov property, we finally deduce that $W(s, y) = \mathbb{E}_{s,y}^\nu [W(s + \sigma_{\mathcal{R}}, Y_{s+\sigma_{\mathcal{R}}})] = f(s, y)$. \square

Remark 1. *The FBP (27a)-(27b) has only one boundary condition, which is typically called “instantaneous stopping” in optimal stopping terminology. The lack of a second boundary condition does not guarantee uniqueness of solution. In many problems, this extra condition comes in the form of smoothly pasting the value and gain functions at the boundary, hence its name “smooth-fit” condition. Specifically, it requires $\partial_y W(s, y) = \partial_y G(s, y)$ for all $(s, y) \in \partial\mathcal{D}$.*

Obtaining the smooth-fit condition is crucial in optimal stopping theory, but also mathematically challenging. As a rule of thumb, if the process enters the stopping set immediately after starting at the OSB, the smooth-fit condition holds (see, e.g., De Angelis and Peskir (2020) and Peskir and Shiryaev (2006, Section 9.1)). The common approach to obtain this (probabilistic) regularity requires smoothness of the OSB.

Provided regularity of the underlying process, it is well-known that monotonicity plus continuity of the OSB suffice for the smooth-fit condition to hold (see e.g., Peskir (2005)), but this framework is too restrictive and not necessarily satisfied in our settings (see "CITE IMAGES BELOW FOR THE GAUSSIAN TERMINAL"). Continuity and piecewise monotonicity is also enough regularity (see. e.g., De Angelis and Peskir (2020, Example 7)) and sensible to expect for a wide class of pinning densities ν . However, intriguingly, this seemingly easy-to-get smoothness has either managed to resist proving attempts or avoided the attention of researches. To the extend of our knowledge Friedman (1964) is the only work devoted to obtain this type of regularity.

Another approach is deriving Lipschitz continuity of the OSB (see Remark 4.5 from De Angelis and Stabile (2019) for a comment on this approach and Proposition 8 in Azze et al. (2024b) for an implementation). This smoothness, however, is challenging to obtain, specially when the coefficients of the underlying process are time-dependent and not explicitly given. The work of De Angelis and Stabile (2019) is paramount in this direction, but imposes some assumptions that prevents its result from scaling to other scenarios... TALK ABOUT Azze et al. (2024b)

TALK ABOUT THAT WE DON'T EVEN HAVE THAT THE BOUNDARY IS MADE OF FUNCTIONS

A random variable Z_1 with distribution ν_1 is said to be smaller in the *likelihood ratio order* than another (independent) random variable with density ν_2 , denoted by $Z_1 \leq_{\text{lr}} Z_2$ (or, in an abuse of notation $\nu_1 \leq_{\text{lr}} \nu_2$), if

$$\mathbb{P}(Z_1 \in \mathcal{A})\mathbb{P}(Z_2 \in \mathcal{B}) \leq \mathbb{P}(Z_1 \in \mathcal{B})\mathbb{P}(Z_2 \in \mathcal{A}), \quad (29)$$

for all Borel sets $\mathcal{A} \leq \mathcal{B}$, in the sense $z_1 \leq z_2$ whenever $z_1 \in \mathcal{A}$ and $z_2 \in \mathcal{B}$. We next compare the value functions associated to different prior terminal densities ordered in the likelihood ratio sense.

Proposition 6 (Ordering of value functions). *Consider two densities ν_1 and ν_2 and denote by W_1 and W_2 to their associated value function (19), respectively. Then,*

$$\nu_1 \leq_{\text{lr}} \nu_2 \implies W_1 \leq W_2.$$

Consequently, $\mathcal{D}_2 \subset \mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{C}_1 \subset \mathcal{C}_2$.

Proof. Let $Z_{i,s,y}$ be the pinning point associated to the posterior density $\nu_{i,s,y}$ of the prior ν_i given $Y_s = y$, for $i = 1, 2$, as defined in (14). Then, for two Borel sets $\mathcal{A} \leq \mathcal{B}$ and taking $f(z) = \frac{\phi(z;y,1-s)}{\phi(z;x_0,1)}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{P}(Z_{1,s,y} \in \mathcal{A})\mathbb{P}(Z_{2,s,y} \in \mathcal{B}) - \mathbb{P}(Z_{1,s,y} \in \mathcal{B})\mathbb{P}(Z_{2,s,y} \in \mathcal{A}) \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{A}} \int_{\mathcal{B}} f(z)f(z')\nu_{2,s,y}(z')\nu_{1,s,y}(z) dz'dz - \int_{\mathcal{A}} \int_{\mathcal{B}} f(z)f(z')\nu_{1,s,y}(z')\nu_{2,s,y}(z) dz'dz \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{A}} \int_{\mathcal{B}} f(z)f(z') (\nu_{2,s,y}(z')\nu_{1,s,y}(z) - \nu_{1,s,y}(z')\nu_{2,s,y}(z)) dz'dz \\ &\leq \max_{\substack{z \in \mathcal{A} \\ z' \in \mathcal{B}}} \{f(z)f(z')\} \int_{\mathcal{A}} \int_{\mathcal{B}} (\nu_{2,s,y}(z')\nu_{1,s,y}(z) - \nu_{1,s,y}(z')\nu_{2,s,y}(z)) dz'dz \leq 0, \end{aligned}$$

which means that $Z_{1,s,y} \leq_{\text{lr}} Z_{2,s,y}$ and, consequently (see, e.g., Theorem 1.C.1 by Shaked and Shanthikumar (2007)) $\mathbb{P}(Z_{1,s,y} \geq z) \leq \mathbb{P}(Z_{2,s,y} \geq z)$ for all $z \in \mathbb{R}$, which results in $\mathbb{E}[Z_{1,s,y}] \leq \mathbb{E}[Z_{2,s,y}]$ and, therefore,

$$\mu^{\nu_1}(s, y) \leq \mu^{\nu_2}(s, y),$$

for all $(s, y) \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}$, with μ^{ν_i} as in (11). Hence (see Corollary 3.1 from Peng and Zhu (2006)), the corresponding rBBs $Y_u^{s,y,(i)}$ hold the relation $Y_u^{s,y,(1)} \leq Y_u^{s,y,(2)}$ $\tilde{\mathbb{P}}$ -a.s. for all $u \in [0, T]$, where $\tilde{\mathbb{P}}$ can be considered as the probability measure induced by a common underlying Brownian motion.

It follows (recall that $y \mapsto G(s, y)$ is increasing) that $W_1 \leq W_2$ and, therefore, $\mathcal{D}_2 \subset \mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{C}_1 \subset \mathcal{C}_2$. \square

A direct consequence of Proposition 6 is that the value function of priors with lower and/or upper bounded support can be controlled by the value function of a Gauss-Markov Bridge (GMB), which is comprehensively studied in Azze et al. (2024b) (see Section 3.2).

Corollary 1 (Bounds for the value function with bounded-supported priors).

Let W_{z^*} be the value function associated to taking $\nu_{z^*} = \delta_{z^*}$, for $z^* \in \mathbb{R}$. That is, Y is a BB with pinning point z^* under $\mathbb{P}^{\nu_{z^*}}$. Let \mathcal{D}_{z^*} and \mathcal{C}_{z^*} be the corresponding stopping and continuation sets, respectively. Then,

(i) if $\text{supp } \nu \subseteq (-\infty, z^*]$, then $W \leq W_{z^*}$ and, consequently, $\mathcal{D}_{z^*} \subset \mathcal{D}$,

(ii) if $\text{supp } \nu \subseteq [z^*, \infty)$, then $W \geq W_{z^*}$ and, consequently, $\mathcal{C}_{z^*} \subset \mathcal{C}$.

Proof. Under (i) (resp. (ii)), the inequality relating the gain functions is a direct consequence of Proposition 6, after checking that $\nu \leq_{\text{lr}} \delta_{z^*}$ (resp. $\delta_{z^*} \leq_{\text{lr}} \nu$). Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (s, y) \in \mathcal{D}_{z^*} &\Rightarrow W(s, y) \leq W_{z^*}(s, y) = G(s, y) \Rightarrow (s, y) \in \mathcal{D}, \\ (\text{resp. } (s, y) \in \mathcal{C}_{z^*} &\Rightarrow W(s, y) \geq W_{z^*}(s, y) > G(s, y) \Rightarrow (s, y) \in \mathcal{C}). \end{aligned}$$

\square

Remark 2. More explicit, yet less useful bounds than the ones derived in Corollary 1 for the value function W , follows from the inequalities

$$\min_{u \in [s, 1]} a_0(u) + \min_{u \in [s, 1]} a_1(u) \widetilde{W}_{z^*}(s, y) \leq W(s, y) \leq \max_{u \in [s, 1]} a_0(u) + \max_{u \in [s, 1]} a_1(u) \widetilde{W}_{z^*}(s, y).$$

Where $\widetilde{W}_{z^*}(s, y) = \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s} \mathbb{E}_{z^*}^{\nu} [Y_{s+\sigma}]$ is the value function associated to optimally stopping a BB with pinning point $Y_1 = z^*$. These bounds, despite not shedding insight about the stopping or the continuation regions, are more explicit and easier to compute. Indeed, the form of $\widetilde{W}_{z^*}(s, y)$ has been known since the early work of Shepp (1969):

$$\widetilde{W}_{z^*}(s, y) = \begin{cases} y, & \text{if } y < b_{z^*}(s), \\ y + 2\pi(1-s)(1-K^2)\phi(y; z^*, 1-s)\Phi((y-z^*)/\sqrt{1-s}), & \text{if } y \geq b_{z^*}(s), \end{cases}$$

for the OSB $b_{z^*}(s) = z^* + K\sqrt{1-s}$, where K is the unique solution of $2\pi(1-K^2)\phi(K; 0, 1)\Phi(K)$, and Φ is the standard-normal distribution.

Finally, in the next proposition, we derive some useful maximal bounds related to the Brownian bridge that we used in previous results.

Lemma 1 (Brownian-bridge maximal bounds).

For a BB $(Y_u^{s,y,z})_{u \in [0, 1-s]}$ from $Y_0^{s,y,z} = y$ to $Y_{1-s}^{s,y,z} = z$, the following holds:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s]} |Y_u^{s,y,z}| \right] \leq \sqrt{1-s} \sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2) + |y| + |z|, \quad (30)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s]} |Y_u^{s,y,z} - y| \right] \leq |z - y| + \sqrt{1-s} \sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2). \quad (31)$$

Additionally, for $s_1 \leq s_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s_1]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_2, z_2}| \right] \\ & \leq (s_2 - s_1) \left(\frac{|y_1| + |z_1| + \sqrt{1-s_1}}{(1-s_1)(1-s_2)} + \frac{1-s_2}{1-s_1} + \frac{|y_1| + |z_1|}{1-s_1} \right) + 2\sqrt{s_2 - s_1} + |y_1 - y_2| + 3|z_1 - z_2|, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where we are assuming that both BBs are driven by the same BM.

Proof. Let $(Y_r)_{r \in [0, 1]}$ be a Brownian bridge from $Y_0 = 0$ to $Y_1 = 0$. Using the well-known result (see, e.g., formulas (4.4) and (4.5) from Biane et al. (2001))

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\sup_{0 \leq r \leq 1} |Y_r| \geq x \right) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} e^{-2n^2 x^2},$$

for $x > 0$, we obtain, by integrating the tail probability and interchanging the sum and integration operators, that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{0 \leq r \leq 1} |Y_r| \right] = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-2n^2 x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi/2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} / n = \sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2).$$

Since

$$Y_u^{s,y,z} = Y_r / \sqrt{1-s} + y + (z-y)r, \quad r = u/(1-s), \quad (33)$$

it follows (30) and (31).

To prove (32), note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s_1]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - Y_{u \wedge (1-s_2)}^{s_2, y_2, z_2}| \right] \\ & \leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s_2]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - Y_u^{s_2, y_2, z_2}| \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [1-s_2, 1-s_1]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - z_2| \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Recall that we are assuming in (32) that the BMs generating both BBs are the same, so we can use the common anticipative representation

$$Y_u^{s_i, y_i, z_i} = y_i + (z_i - y_i) \frac{u}{1-s_i} + \left(B_u - \frac{u}{1-s_i} B_{1-s_i} \right),$$

from where we get the following for the first addend in (34):

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s_2]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - Y_u^{s_2, y_2, z_2}| \right] \\ & = \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [0, 1-s_2]} \left| y_1 \left(1 - \frac{u}{1-s_1} \right) - y_2 \left(1 - \frac{u}{1-s_2} \right) + (z_1 - B_{1-s_1}) \frac{u}{1-s_1} - (z_2 - B_{1-s_2}) \frac{u}{1-s_2} \right| \right] \\ & \leq (|y_1| + |z_1| + \mathbb{E} [|B_{1-s_1}|]) \frac{s_2 - s_1}{(1-s_1)(1-s_2)} + |y_1 - y_2| + |z_1 - z_2| + \mathbb{E} [|B_{1-s_1} - B_{1-s_2}|], \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where we used the triangle inequality $|a_1b_1 - a_2b_2| \leq |a_1||b_1 - b_2| + |a_1 - a_2||b_2|$. We recall that

$$\mathbb{E}[|B_{1-s_1}|] = \sqrt{1-s_1}\sqrt{2/\pi}, \quad \mathbb{E}[|B_{1-s_1} - B_{1-s_1}|] = \sqrt{s_2-s_1}\sqrt{2/\pi}. \quad (36)$$

To handle the second addend in (34), note that $Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - z_2 = Y_u^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2}$ and, therefore, one can get the following inequality by using (30),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [1-s_2, 1-s_1]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1, z_1} - z_2| \right] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E} \left[\sup_{u \in [1-s_2, 1-s_1]} |Y_u^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2}| \mid Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2} \right] \right] \\ &\leq \sqrt{s_2-s_1}\sqrt{\pi/2} \ln(2) + \mathbb{E} \left[|Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2}| \right] + |z_1 - z_2|. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Since $Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2} \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta, \gamma^2)$, with

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &:= \mathbb{E} \left[Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2} \right] = (y_1 - z_2) + (z_1 - y_1) \frac{1-s_2}{1-s_1} = (y_1 - z_1) \frac{s_2-s_1}{1-s_1} + (z_1 - z_2), \\ \gamma^2 &:= \text{Var} \left[Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2} \right] = (s_2 - s_1) \frac{1-s_2}{1-s_1}, \end{aligned}$$

it follows that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[|Y_{1-s_2}^{s_1, y_1 - z_2, z_1 - z_2}| \right] = \gamma \sqrt{2/\pi} e^{-\frac{\theta^2}{2\gamma^2}} + \theta (1 - 2\Phi(-\theta/\gamma)) \leq \gamma + |\theta|. \quad (38)$$

Plugging (36) and (38) back into (35) and (37) respectively, and merging the results into (34), one obtains, after grouping common terms, inequality (32). \square

3.1 The Gaussian prior

Consider now the prior terminal density ν to be normal, that is, $\nu(z) = \phi(z; \theta, \gamma^2)$ for some $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\gamma^2 > 0$. In such case, by identifying the ratio and multiplication of normal densities as another scaled normal density (see Lemma 2), the drift function in (11) takes the form $\mu^\nu(s, y) = (\theta_{s,y} - y)/(1-s)$, for

$$\theta_{s,y} = \gamma_s^2 \left(\frac{y}{1-s} + \frac{\theta}{\gamma^2} - x_0 \right), \quad \gamma_s^2 = \left(\frac{1}{1-s} + \frac{1}{\gamma^2} - 1 \right)^{-1}.$$

That is, $\mu^\nu(s, y) = a(s)x + b(s)$, with

$$a(s) = \frac{1}{1-s} \left(\frac{\gamma_s^2}{1-s} - 1 \right), \quad b(s) = \frac{\gamma_s^2}{1-s} \left(\frac{\gamma_s^2}{1-s} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{\theta}{\gamma^2} - x_0 \right).$$

Hence, the gain process $G_s = G(s, Y_s)$ solves the SDE

$$dG_s = (A(s)X_s + B(s)) ds + C(s)dB_s^\nu, \quad (39)$$

for

$$A(s) = \frac{a_1'(s)}{a_1(s)} + a(s), \quad B(s) = a_0'(s) - \left(\frac{a_1'(s)}{a_1(s)} + a(s) \right) a_0(s) + a_1(s)b(s), \quad C(s) = a_1(s).$$

Since A , B and C are continuously differentiable in $[0, 1]$ (recall that a_0 and a_1 has the same regularity and a_1 is strictly positive), then Theorem 4.1 alongside Remarks 1 and 2 from Azze et al. (2024a) ensure that the $\mathcal{D} = \{(s, y) : y \geq b(s)\}$, where the OSB b is the unique solution, among the class of positive, continuous, bounded variation functions, of the the Volterra-type integral equation

$$b(s) = \mathbb{E} [Z_{s, b(s)}] + \int_s^1 \mathbb{E}_{s, b(s)} [(A(u)Y_u + B(u)) \mathbb{1}(Y_u \geq b(u))] du. \quad (40)$$

Moreover, $b(1) = \max\{0, \}$ (WEIRD!!), and b is Lipschitz continuous in all sets of the type $[0, s']$, for $0 \leq s' < 1$ (see Proposition 3.3 in Azze et al. (2024a)).

Remark 3. A direct application of the work in Azze et al. (2024a) actually leads (by taking a null strike price and interest rate in the paper and checking Remark 2 *ibid.*) to the solution of the OSP $\widetilde{W}^+(s, y) := \sup_{\sigma \leq 1-s} \mathbb{E}_{s,y} \left[(\widetilde{Y}_{s+\sigma})^+ \right]$, for (see Remark 1 in the paper)

$$dY_s = \widetilde{A}(s)(\widetilde{B}(s) - Y_s)ds + \widetilde{C}(s)dB_s. \quad (41)$$

At first, these two apparent differences with respect to our settings might induce doubts about (40) being obtained from Azze et al. (2024a). We show here that the seemingly different settings are actually the same.

First notice that taking the positive-part gain function does not change the resulting OSB versus an identity gain, as both gain functions coincide in the positive space axis, where the stopping sets of both regions are.

Second, the SDE is equivalent to (39) whenever A does not vanishes in $[0, 1]$. However, when $A(s)$ vanishes at some points, taking the truncated function

$$A_\varepsilon(s) := A(s)\mathbb{1}(|A(s)| \geq \varepsilon) + \varepsilon\mathbb{1}(A(s) \in [0, \varepsilon)) - \varepsilon\mathbb{1}(A(s) \in (-\varepsilon, 0)),$$

for $\varepsilon > 0$, guarantees that the process $Y_s^{(\varepsilon)}$ defined by replacing A with A_ε suits the settings in Azze et al. (2024a). Since $|A_\varepsilon(s) - A(s)| \leq \varepsilon$ for all $s \in [0, 1]$ and $d(Y_s^{(\varepsilon)} - Y_s) = (A_\varepsilon(s)Y_s^{(\varepsilon)} - A(s)Y_s)ds$, a standard Gronwall-type argument establishes that $M_{s,y} := \mathbb{E}_{s,y} \left[\sup_{u \leq 1-s} |Y_{s+u} - Y_{s+u}^{(\varepsilon)}| \right] \xrightarrow{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} 0$ uniformly in (s, y) in compacts of $[0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}$. Hence, the associated value functions W^ε and W (and, therefore, their corresponding OSBs) hold the same type of convergence as ε becomes arbitrarily small. Indeed, $|W^{(\varepsilon)}(s, y) - W(s, y)| \leq M_{s,y}$ (see (24)).

Finally, equation (40) can also be obtained directly reproducing the approach taken in Azze et al. (2024a) with minor tweaks. Indeed, taking the positive-part gain function and introducing a discount makes nothing but more complicated the analysis of the OSP, and all the arguments displayed in the paper are applicable to derive the same regularity of the value function and OSB, including the free-boundary equation (40).

3.2 The Dirac delta prior

Consider now a Dirac-delta prior terminal density, that is, $\nu = \delta_{z^*}$ for some $z^* \in \mathbb{R}$. In such case, $Y = (Y_s)_{s \in [0,1]}$ is a BB with pinning point z^* under \mathbb{P}^ν and, hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[Y_s] &= a_0(s) + a_1(s)(x_0 + (z^* - x_0)s), \\ \text{Cov}[Y_s, Y_{s'}] &= R_1(\min(s, s'))R_2(\max(s, s')), \end{aligned}$$

for $R_1(s) = a_1(s)s$ and $R_2(s) = a_1(s)(1-s)$. Therefore, Y is a Gauss-Markov bridge in the sense specified in Azze et al. (2024b). If we furthermore assume that a_1 and a_2 are twice continuously differentiable (which boils down to ask for continuously differentiable coefficients α , β and ζ in (1)), the results in Azze et al. (2024b) implies (see Section 5 *ibid.*) that $\mathcal{D} = \{(s, y) : y \geq b(s)\}$, for the OSB $b : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ characterized as the unique solution, among the class of continuous functions of bounded variation, of the free-boundary equation

$$b(s) = z^* - \int_s^1 \mathbb{E}_{s,b(s)} [A(u)(B(u) - Y_u)\mathbb{1}(Y_u \geq b(u))] du, \quad (42)$$

for

$$A(s) = \frac{1}{1-s} - \frac{a'_1(s)}{a_1(s)}, \quad B(s) = \frac{\left(a'_0(s) - \frac{a'_1(s)}{a_1(s)} a_0(s) \right) (1-s) + a_1(s)z^* + a_0(s)}{A(s)(1-s)},$$

such that $dY_s = A(s)(B(s) - Y_s)ds + a_1(s)dB_s^\nu$.

Appendix

Proposition 7. *Let $Y = (Y_s)_{s \in [0,1]}$ be a standard BM. Then, under the probability \mathbb{P}^ν defined such that $\mathbb{P}^\nu(\cdot \mid Y_1 \sim \nu)$, Y is the unique strong solution of the SDE (10).*

Proof. Denote by $p_{s_0, y_0}(s, \cdot)$ and $p_{s_0, y_0}^\nu(s, \cdot)$ to the transition densities of Y under \mathbb{P} and \mathbb{P}^ν , respectively, starting at (s_0, y_0) and transitioning to (s, \cdot) .

The Markovianity of Y implies that

$$p_{0, x_0}^\nu(s, y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} p_{0, x_0}^z(s, y) \nu(z) dz = p_{0, x_0}(s, y) \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{p_{s, y}(1, z)}{p(1, z)} \nu(z) dz = p_{0, x_0}(s, y) \psi^\nu(s, y),$$

where $\psi^\nu(s, y)$ is defined at (12) and $p_{0, x_0}^z(s, \cdot)$ is the transition density of a Brownian bridge with pinning point z .

This means that $\psi^\nu(s, Y_s)$ is the Radon–Nikodym derivative $d\mathbb{P}^\nu/d\mathbb{P}$. Hence (see, e.g., Jacod and Shiryaev (2003, Theorem 3.4, Chapter III)), since \mathbb{P}^ν is absolute continuous with respect to \mathbb{P} (their Radon–Nikodym derivative is positive), the density process $\psi^\nu(s, Y_s)$ is a \mathbb{P} -martingale. Therefore, the drift term in the Itô expansion of $\psi^\nu(s, Y_s)$ vanishes, resulting in

$$\begin{aligned} d\psi^\nu(s, Y_s) &= \partial_y \psi^\nu(s, Y_s) dY_s = \frac{\partial_y \psi^\nu(s, Y_s)}{\psi^\nu(s, Y_s)} \psi_{0, y}^\nu(s, Y_s) dY_s \\ &= \partial_y \ln(\psi^\nu)(s, Y_s) \psi^\nu(s, Y_s) dY_s. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Girsanov's theorem yields (10). □

Lemma 2. *Let f_i be a normal density with mean θ_i and variance γ_i^2 , for $i = 1, 2, 3$, such that $\gamma_1 < \gamma_3$. Consider the constants*

$$\gamma^2 = \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_1^2} + \frac{1}{\gamma_2^2} - \frac{1}{\gamma_3^2} \right)^{-1}, \quad \theta = \gamma^2 \left(\frac{\theta_1}{\gamma_1^2} + \frac{\theta_2}{\gamma_2^2} - \frac{\theta_3}{\gamma_3^2} \right), \quad C = \frac{\theta_1^2}{2\gamma_1^2} + \frac{\theta_2^2}{2\gamma_2^2} - \frac{\theta_3^2}{2\gamma_3^2} - \frac{\theta^2}{2\gamma^2}.$$

Then,

$$f_1(z)f_2(z)/f_3(z) = \frac{\gamma_3}{\gamma_1\gamma_2} \gamma \exp\{-C\} f(z) \tag{43}$$

where f is a normal density with mean θ and variance γ^2 .

Proof. Notice that

$$f_1(z)f_2(z)/f_3(z) = \frac{\gamma_3}{\sqrt{2\pi}\gamma_1\gamma_2} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{(z-\theta_1)^2}{2\gamma_1^2} + \frac{(z-\theta_2)^2}{2\gamma_2^2} - \frac{(z-\theta_3)^2}{2\gamma_3^2}\right)\right\}.$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(z-\theta_1)^2}{2\gamma_1^2} + \frac{(z-\theta_2)^2}{2\gamma_2^2} - \frac{(z-\theta_3)^2}{2\gamma_3^2} &= \frac{z^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_1^2} + \frac{1}{\gamma_2^2} - \frac{1}{\gamma_3^2} \right) - z \left(\frac{\theta_1}{\gamma_1^2} + \frac{\theta_2}{\gamma_2^2} - \frac{\theta_3}{\gamma_3^2} \right) + \left(\frac{\theta_1^2}{2\gamma_1^2} + \frac{\theta_2^2}{2\gamma_2^2} - \frac{\theta_3^2}{2\gamma_3^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{(z-\theta)^2}{2\gamma^2} + C, \end{aligned}$$

from where it follows (43). □

References

- Azze, A., D’Auria, B., and García-Portugués, E. (2024a). Optimal exercise of american options under time-dependent ornstein–uhlenbeck processes. *Stochastics*, 96(1):921–946.
- Azze, A., D’Auria, B., and García-Portugués, E. (2024b). Optimal stopping of gauss–markov bridges. *Adv. Appl. Probab.*, page 1–34.
- Biane, P., Pitman, J., and Yor, M. (2001). Probability laws related to the Jacobi theta and Riemann zeta functions, and Brownian excursions. *Bull. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 38(4):435–465.
- Borisov, I. S. (1983). On a criterion for Gaussian random processes to be Markovian. *Theory Probab. Its Appl.*, 27(4):863–865.
- Buonocore, A., Caputo, L., Nobile, A. G., and Pirozzi, E. (2013). On some time-non-homogeneous linear diffusion processes and related bridges. *Sci. Math. Jpn.*, 76(1):55–77.
- De Angelis, T. and Peskir, G. (2020). Global C^1 regularity of the value function in optimal stopping problems. *Ann. Appl. Probab.*, 30(3):1007–1031.
- De Angelis, T. and Stabile, G. (2019). On Lipschitz continuous optimal stopping boundaries. *SIAM J. Control Optim.*, 57(1):402–436.
- Friedman, A. (1964). *Partial Differential Equations of Parabolic Type*. Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs.
- Jacod, J. and Shiryaev, A. N. (2003). *Limit Theorems for Stochastic Processes*, volume 288 of *A Series of Comprehensive Studies in Mathematics*. Springer, Berlin, 2nd edition.
- Krylov, N. V. (1980). *Controlled Diffusion Processes*. Stochastic Modelling and Applied Probability. Springer-Verlag.
- Mehr, C. B. and McFadden, J. A. (1965). Certain properties of Gaussian processes and their first-passage times. *J. R. Stat. Soc. Ser. B Methodol.*, 27(3):505–522.
- Peng, S. and Zhu, X. (2006). Necessary and sufficient condition for comparison theorem of 1-dimensional stochastic differential equations. *Stoch. Process. Their Appl.*, 116(3):370–380.
- Peskir, G. (2005). On the American option problem. *Math. Finance*, 15(1):169–181.
- Peskir, G. and Shiryaev, A. (2006). *Optimal Stopping and Free-Boundary Problems*. Lectures in Mathematics. ETH Zürich. Birkhäuser, Basel.
- Shaked, M. and Shanthikumar, J. G., editors (2007). *Stochastic Orders*. Springer Series in Statistics. Springer, New York, NY, 1st edition.
- Shepp, L. A. (1969). Explicit solutions to some problems of optimal stopping. *Ann. Math. Stat.*, 40(3):993–1010.
- Villani, C. (2003). *Topics in Optimal Transportation*. Graduate studies in mathematics. American Mathematical Society.